

Lent is Gift of Joy, Says Visiting Jesuit Superior General

Arturo Sosa SJ

Prayer, contemplation, meditation and worship bring about our reconciliation with God, said Fr Sosa. Jesuit Superior General Father Arturo Sosa, who is on a visit to India, stressed the urgency of reconciliation with God, humanity and nature during his Ash Wednesday Mass in Pune.

“We need urgently to reconcile ourselves with God, fellow human beings and with nature,” Father Sosa said on March 6 while celebrating the Eucharist on the first day of the season of Lent at Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth (JDV) seminary.

Father Sosa maintained that the season of Lent is a gift of joy. Two words here are striking: gift and joy. Lent is God's gift to us, and it brings us great joy. The joy of returning to God — the God who fills us with joy, restores us and reconciles us with Himself, with all His children, and with all His creatures, he said.

He added that Jesus proposes very precise and practical steps to realize this reconciliation. The three steps are: prayer, fasting and alms-giving.”

The global head of Jesuits, also the JDV Chancellor, want-

ed the 1,100 staff and students of the seminary to engage with the three steps and “strive for the triple reconciliation — with God, with others, and with nature.”

Prayer, contemplation, meditation and worship bring about our reconciliation with God. Alms-giving makes us aware of the poor--the millions struggling to “survive in our selfish world,” he said. Alms-giving means “not only giving what we have but...it also is self-giving. It reconciles us with all of humankind,” the Jesuit said.

Fasting creates an awareness of God's generosity through the gifts of nature. “Fasting could help us to be reconciled with mother earth (creation) and with all God's creatures,” Father Sosa added. The president of JDV Father Selva Rathinam welcomed Father Sosa explaining the service of the major seminary.

The JDV has 800 students and 33 professors in its faculties of Philosophy and Theology. The students represent 82 dioceses and 83 different religious congregations. Father Francis Gonsalves, Dean of theology faculty, introduced the superior general.

Jesuit's South Asian provincial and JDV vice-chancellor Father George Pattery and Papal Seminary Rector Father Bhausahab Sansare joined others to felicitate Father Sosa.

Two of his General Assistants--Father Lisbert D'Souza and Vernon D'Cunha---and Father Juan Antonio Guerrero Alves, Delegate for the International Houses in Rome, are accompanying Father Sosa.

(Taken from <http://m.ucanindia.in/news/lent-is-gift-of-joy-says-visiting-jesuit-superior-39453.html>. This homily was delivered on Ash Wednesday, March 6, 2019)

General's Visit: Lifting Up our Spirit

Jacob Kulangara

Superior General of the Society of Jesus, Arturo Sosa came to De Nobili College, Pune on 5th March 2019. He stayed in the campus until 7th afternoon. During his visit, he celebrated the Ash Wednesday mass in Papal Seminary for the whole campus, had lunch in Papal Seminary, dinner in DNC and attended several meetings with scholastics, seminarians and staff. Those were days full of activities and programmes.

Prior to his visit, DNC had a few months of planning and preparations. Many days were allotted to beautifying the house, preparing the rooms and cleaning up the campus for the visit of the General. Under the leadership of Fr. Edward (Rector), the whole house was involved in the preparation. He meticulously planned everything in minute detail in consultation with the POSA (George Pattery) and General's Assistants Frs. Lisbert and Vernon. It was nice seeing the whole house actively and tirelessly working together for a purpose. We had to do a lot of meticulous planning so that nothing was left undone. It has to be noted that the General himself was least bothered about luxury and pomp in any way. But as protocol demands, we had to make the necessary preparations. We were aware that the task was very important, and all of us took it seriously.

My personal impressions of the General and his visit are very deep and full of joy and satisfaction. It was definitely an experience of grace. As the minister of the house, I had to be with him on several occasions. Without hesitation, I would say that I cherished every moment I was with him. He is a man full of life and enthusiasm and enjoys living his life to the full. He enjoyed the company of not only the staff but also the young scholastics. He easily mingled with the scholastics; during the meal, he easily moved around with them. And scholastics took selfies with him at will. Fr. Ted eagerly awaited his visit, and it was a heart warming sight to see the two of them when they met. Fr. Ted had happily offered his room for renovation given the General's Visit. (*Contd on p. 19*)